

Synthesis and Fungicidal Studies of Niobium(v) Complexes with *N*-Alkylphenothiazines

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N-Alkylphenothiazines (NAP) find extensive applications in the fields of medicine^{1,2} and chemical analysis³. The importance of the toxicity in the compounds containing nitrogen and sulphur have been well-established in many fungicides⁴ and that the metal complexes have greater activity than the ligands themselves. Recently, seven-coordinated pentagonal bipyramid niobium(v) complex⁵, five- and six-coordinated niobium complexes of distorted octahedral structure⁶, and binuclear bridging dialkyl carbamates of niobium complexes have been characterised⁷. The authors report here the isolation, characterisation and fungicidal activities of dioxobridged binuclear niobium(v) complexes with six *N*-alkylphenothiazines.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are non-hygroscopic, stable in air for long periods at room temperature and do not possess sharp melting points. The complexes are insoluble in water and other common organic solvents but are soluble in dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulphoxide. The molar conductances in DMF are in the range 70–95 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ at 10^{-3} M concentration, indicating them as 1 : 1 electrolytes. The magnetic susceptibility values for all the complexes determined at room temperature by Gouy method proved to be diamagnetic as expected for

niobium(v) complexes.

Electronic spectra of the complexes show no absorption peaks in the visible region. The free ligands show sharp band at 260–280 nm, while their corresponding complexes exhibit sharp peaks at 260–288 nm due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. A weak ligand band at 306–312 nm shifted hypsochromically to 300–308 nm in the spectra of their complexes due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition.

The broad infrared bands at 2 970–2 830 cm^{-1} in the spectra of free NAP are assigned to the heterocyclic nitrogen atom carrying the alkyl side-chain². In the spectra of the corresponding complexes, these bands are either absent or shifted by 10–30 cm^{-1} to higher frequency indicating the coordination of heterocyclic nitrogen atom to the metal. A broad band observed at 2 600–2 350 cm^{-1} in spectra of the ligands correspond to the $-\text{CH}_2\text{NR}_2\text{H}^+\text{X}^-$ (R = methyl; X = chloride or phosphate). The absence of this band in the spectra of the niobium(v)-NAP complexes, indicates that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the side-chain is also a site of coordination. Thus *N*-alkylphenothiazines act as bidentate chelating agents. The coordination of bidentate tartrate is confirmed by the bands at 1 710–1 675 cm^{-1} (asymmetric COO vibration) and 1 400–1 375 cm^{-1} (symmetric COO vibration)⁸. The bands observed in the region

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY (% INHIBITION) AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS(%) OF NIOBIUM(V)-NAP COMPLEXES

Compd./ Colour (M.p., °C)	Λ_{M^*} Ω^{-1} $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	<i>B. theobromae</i>			<i>C. paradoxa</i>			<i>L. trabea</i>		
		0.01	0.25	0.5	0.01	0.25	0.5	0.01	0.25	0.5
[NbO(CP)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Cream (122–25)	80	9.5	26.5	60.3	10.5	22.3	62.5	9.6	22.2	60.6
[NbO(PM)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Blue (130–34)	75	10.6	24.8	62.2	9.8	24.6	63.6	9.3	23.6	61.3
[NbO(TFP)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Cream (129–32)	90	10.8	29.8	61.6	11.3	26.3	61.8	10.2	21.8	65.5
[NbO(PP)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Yellow (110–14)	85	11.3	28.2	64.6	10.8	27.8	64.3	11.4	24.6	64.3
[NbO(PZ)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Pink (132–35)	94	10.2	26.6	63.8	9.6	25.6	62.6	12.6	22.3	62.8
[NbO(PPC)(C ₄ H ₄ O ₆) ₂] ₂ C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ Yellow (123–26)	70	9.8	27.3	64.2	10.3	24.9	65.6	10.8	23.9	61.8
Niobium(v) solutions	–	2–4	8–9	18–20	3–4	6–8	20–21	3–5	7–9	20–22
NAP	–	2–3	5–6	8–10	4–5	6–7	8–10	2–3	5–6	8–10

490–470 cm^{-1} correspond to Nb Nb bridge bond. The far-ir spectra of the complexes exhibit new bands at 380–350 (Nb–N) cm^{-1} .

¹H nmr spectra of the ligands and the corresponding complexes exhibit chemical shift at lower fields for N–CH₃ protons which appear for the complexes at δ 2.75–2.90 compared to that in the free ligands (δ 2.55–2.70). This down-field shift in the signal of the complexes may be attributed to the coordinating effect of the nitrogen atom of the alkyl side-chain which results in a deshielding of protons attached to it as evidenced from ir spectral studies discussed above.

Thermogravimetric studies indicate the decomposition of complexes with the loss of tartrate and organic moiety followed by the formation of Nb₂O₅ in the temperature ranges 140–160°, 200–250° and 450–500°. The complexes are stable upto 135° and start decomposing at 140–250°. The weight-loss become constant at 450–500°. The weight-loss observed is in agreement with that calculated on the basis of stoichiometry proposed for the complexes.

Antifungal studies : The antifungal activity of the ligands and the complexes was assayed against three different fungi namely, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, *Ceratocystis paradoxa* and *Lenzites trabea* at 0.01, 0.25 and 0.5% concentrations by the Batemann poisoned food technique¹⁰. The experiment was conducted using nutrient agar medium. The solutions of NAP ligands and complexes prepared in 10% DMF were poured into petri plates containing nutrient agar after solidification. The test fungi were taken as 2 mm dishes from 7 days old culture and experiment was carried out with four replicates per treatment and incubation carried out at 22 ± 2° for 9 days. The radial growth of the colony was recorded after the completion of incubation and the mean diameter in each concentration was recorded. It is found that maximum concentrations of *N*-alkylphenothiazines, niobium(v) solution and their corresponding complexes required to control the growth of the three fungi are 15–20, 4–6 and 0.01–0.5% respectively. The screening data are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Niobium pentoxide and *N*-alkylphenothiazines were used as received. Reagent grade ether was dried over sodium wire and commercial ethanol refluxed over calcium oxide for 6 h followed by distillation.

Niobium(v) solution was prepared¹¹ by fusion of niobium pentoxide (0.125 g) with potassium pyrosulphate (5 g) and leachig with 10% tartaric acid solution (30 ml). The solution was then diluted to 250 ml using distilled water and used for the preparation of complexes. An ethanolic solution of *N*-alkylphenothiazines (1 mmol, 25 ml) was added to an aqueous solution of niobium(v) (1 mmol, 25 ml) slowly with stirring. The resulting niobium(v)-NAP complex was washed with ethanol followed by diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂.

C, H and N were analysed at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Niobium was estimated gravimetrically by direct ignition to Nb₂O₅. Tartrate was determined volumetrically using chloramine-T. The analytical data of the compounds were in close agreement with the calculated values. Ir spectra were recorded on a Biorad SPC 3200 spectrophotometer, far-ir spectra (polythene disc) on a Polytech 30 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (dimethyl formamide) on a Jasco UVIDEK-610 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Hitachi R-600 spectrometer. The electrical conductance of the complexes was measured in 10⁻³ M DMF solutions using a Systronic 304 conductivity meter. Thermal analysis was carried out on a Stanton Red Craft TG 750/770 electrobalance at a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ in static air. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant.

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